

FILE_INFORMATION_IN-ENGLISH

Instruments to measure the variables

Civic Engagement (EN).

Dimension 'Responsibility.' (en1)

en11. I feel responsible for my community.

en12. I should make a difference in my community.

en13. I believe that I have a responsibility to help others.

en14. I am committed to serving my community.

en15. I believe that all citizens have a responsibility to their community.

en16. I believe it is essential to stay informed about community issues.

en17. I believe that it is important to volunteer.

en18. I believe that it is important to financially support charitable organizations.

Dimension 'Participation' (en2).

en21. I am involved in a structured volunteer position(s) in the community.

en22. When working with others, I make positive changes in the community.

en23. I help members of my community.

en24. I stay informed of events in my community.

en26. I contribute to charitable organizations within the community.

Perceived risk of corruption-driven EA (PR).

pr1. Dimension: Importance.

pr11. Non-important vs. very important.

pr12. Non-essential / Essential.

pr13. Not indispensable / Indispensable.

pr14. Non-fundamental / Fundamental.

pr2. Dimension: Time.

pr21. Short-term / Long-term.

pr22. Non-urgent / Urgent.

pr23. Not pressing / Pressing.

pr24. Unavoidable / Avoidable.

pr3. Dimension: Control.

pr31. Uncontrollable / Controllable.

pr32. Unverifiable / Verifiable.

pr33. Not supervisable / Supervisable.

pr34. Uninspectable / Inspectable.

Intention to report EA (WH).

wh11. If I had evidence of an act of corruption, I would feel personally obligated to report it.

wh12. I would denounce a case of corruption, even if I had to spend a day testifying in court.

wh13. In our society, it is considered a positive act for individuals to report cases of corruption for which they have evidence.

wh21. I would notify the police if I had evidence of an ecological attack (*).

wh22. Ecological attacks should be reported to the police, not just on social networks.

(*). Proposed in the pretest.